

Newsletter Year 3 March 2026

EDGE **A-IQ READY**

A-IQ Ready

Artificial Intelligence for Realtime Distributed Systems at the Edge

Over the past three years, the A-IQ Ready project has explored innovative approaches to building intelligent, autonomous Electronic Components and Systems (ECS) for Europe's digital future. By combining technologies such as AI edge continuum orchestration, distributed collaborative intelligence, and quantum sensing, the project has contributed to the development of smarter, more adaptive digital infrastructures. This final newsletter highlights the project's key achievements, technological progress, and impact, supporting Europe's transition toward a human-centric and sustainable Society 5.0.

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Project coordinator:

Reiner John
AVL List GmbH

Duration:

01.01.2023 - 31.03.2026

**Participating
organizations:**

50

**Number of
countries:**

15

**Requested EU
contribution:**

~€ 10,6M

Total investment:

~€ 33,7M

The A-IQ Ready Evolution: Innovation in AI and Quantum Sensing

After three years of collaboration among 50 partners across Europe, the A-IQ Ready project has delivered advanced technologies in AI-enabled sensing, autonomous systems, and edge computing, enabling intelligent systems to operate reliably even in complex and harsh environments. By combining advanced Quantum sensors, energy-efficient AI processors, distributed diagnostics, and hybrid computing platforms, the project significantly advanced the capabilities of **autonomous monitoring**, **decision-making**, and **industrial automation**.

Advanced Quantum sensors

Energy-efficient AI processors

Distributed diagnostics

Hybrid computing platforms

Advancing European High-Tech Innovation and Industrial Competitiveness

These innovations strengthen European industrial competitiveness by supporting the development of new high-tech products, platforms, and engineering tools for sectors such as automotive, robotics, logistics, and infrastructure monitoring. The project also contributes to the European semiconductor and embedded systems ecosystem through the use of open architectures and scalable AI solutions for edge and hybrid computing.

Enhancing Safety and Resilience in Critical Systems

In addition, the project enhances safety, efficiency, and resilience in critical environments. Technologies developed for autonomous navigation, human-machine interaction, and infrastructure monitoring improve operational safety and enable earlier detection of potential risks.

Promoting Sustainable Industrial Practices

Finally, the project promotes more sustainable industrial practices by enabling energy-efficient computing, optimized logistics operations, and smarter monitoring systems that reduce resource consumption and environmental impact.

A-IQ Ready Key Demonstrators: Project Technical Achievements

SC1-SC8

SC1: Safe Co-existence of Automated and Manual Transport at Industrial Sites

SC1.1

Semi-closed industrial sites are a key emerging domain for applying connected and automated vehicle technology. The motivation for this includes increased productivity and continuity of operations. The safety challenges are more manageable than on public roads since only trained personnel with safety equipment are allowed to work at the site, and the driving speeds are often modest. This led to the development of an on-board software (SW) platform with safety features and the capability to operate in mixed traffic. The demo included two pilot cases: The Kouvola case and the Rauma case.

The Kouvola case (SC1-D01) focused on automating container loading and unloading to/from rail wagons with a reach stacker, complemented by autonomous container transport with an autonomous terminal tractor. Field tests with the Terminal Tractor and Reach Stacker were successfully conducted in Tampere, Finland, and in Ljungby, Sweden.

The Rauma case (SC1-D02) involved automating log transport with a sawmill area. The goal was to transfer log cages between various loading and unloading locations using an Automated Guided Vehicle (AGV). The AGV vehicle and the log cages to transfer are ready for fully computerized control.

Besides the vehicles, their remote operator support was also implemented. This support includes database response models, Prompt-to-SQL model training, and the remote operator portal including integration of Reach Stacker data playback and direct SQL-queries with a Large Language Model response.

During the demos, two different sensor suits were tested: Lidar + camera during the automated driving, and lidar + spreader cameras during the spreader alignment and automatic container handling.

The safety aspects of the self-operating vehicles in both demo sites were analyzed by applying Preliminary Hazard Analysis (PHA) and System Theoretic Process Analysis (STPA). Also the approach described in UL4600 – Safety Standard for Autonomous Vehicles – was applied.

Demo leader: VTT

Partners involved: Kalmar Finland Oy, Unikie Oy, Mantsinen Oy, Vaisto Oy and IMA s.r.o.

Figure 1. Kalmar Reach Stacker with autonomous loading and unloading of containers.

As part of the project, several different use cases were implemented. This case focuses on Metsä Group's Rauma sawmill, where the goal was to explore autonomous log transportation in an industrial setting. The aim was to develop a solution that could automatically transport logs from the train unloading area to the sawmill's feed table. The solution is based on Unikie's autonomous driving system, which uses sensors installed around the factory area to create a real-time digital twin of the environment. This system controls a ground vehicle developed by Mantsinen, capable of transporting log cages while monitoring surrounding activity. Operational safety was a key research focus due to the semi-open nature of the environment, where other vehicles and pedestrians may be present.

After three years of research and development, the concept was successfully tested in October 2025 at the Rauma sawmill by Unikie and Mantsinen. The site was equipped with sensors, cabling, and a server that enabled the ground vehicle to drive from behind the drying building to the sawmill's feed table. A real-world use case was tested—albeit on a smaller scale—by transporting full log cages to the unloading area and returning empty cages to the loading point. Safety was also tested by walking in front of the vehicle, and driving precision was validated with sub-10 cm accuracy when positioning under the log cages.

All tests were successful, despite installation challenges due to a tight schedule. The ground vehicle was able to repeatedly position itself under the log cages and transport full loads along a predefined route. It stopped reliably—whether empty or loaded—when a person entered its safety zone. The concept worked as intended, and no obstacles were identified that would prevent commercial deployment.

We are proud to say that this is one of the world's first solutions where a heavy ground vehicle can move autonomously and safely among people and manually operated machines in an industrial environment.

Figure 2. Testing environment at Metsä Group's Rauma sawmill.

Figure 3. Testing operational safety with full log cage.

SC2: Search & Rescue (SAR) and Emergency Response for Civil Safety

Single-robot

SC2.1

Demonstrator SC2.1 represents a robotic platform capable of supporting Search and Rescue (SAR) operations in subterranean and GNSS-denied environments. As part of SC2, its purpose is to validate autonomous localization, mapping, and survivor detection capabilities under real-world underground conditions at the tunnel facilities at Zentrum am Berg (ZaB). The platform combines robust hardware, advanced perception technologies, and AI-driven algorithms to enable autonomous mission execution in challenging, GPS-inaccessible tunnel systems.

SC2.1 is an Unmanned Ground Vehicle (UGV) equipped with a suite of specialized sensors (e.g. LiDAR, thermal camera) and an onboard computing platform tailored to execute enhanced algorithms enabling autonomous navigation and AI-based survivor detection for complex underground missions. Due to an extensive simulation study, robust open-source SLAM algorithms dealing well with featureless environments were selected to be implemented on the UGV. The Survivor Detection pipeline aims to detect and estimate the poses of potential human survivors near the robot platform. Two approaches are introduced, an onboard method utilizing thermal images and LiDAR pointcloud, and an offboard method leveraging only thermal images. Data communication interfaces are established to transmit survivor positions and mission updates to emergency personnel. A wireless system simulator provides information about relevant communication attributes within the tunnels. Additionally, SC2.1 supports a complementary feasibility study of magnetic field-based mapping and self-localization, evaluating the potential of magnetometer signals as an alternative positioning method in underground settings.

Figure 4. SAR real-world demonstrator vehicle at ZaB.

SC2.1 combines multiple innovative elements that push the state of the art in subterranean SAR robotics:

- **Autonomous operation in GNSS-denied subterranean environments:** SC2.1 successfully performs localization and supports navigation without GNSS which is an essential requirement for tunnel missions.
- **AI-supported survivor detection:** Integrated perception algorithms allow the UGV to identify survivors and provide their estimated positions to human responders, enabling faster and safer rescue operations.
- **Quantum sensing supported localization (future integration):** In the context of SC2.1 the incorporation of a quantum sensor from SC5 will further elevate localization precision under highly degraded conditions.
- **Real-world validation:** SC2.1 is deployed at the ZaB facilities, a unique European-scale experimental site offering realistic tunnel geometries and material properties.

These innovations allow SC2.1 to act as a reference platform for safe, autonomous, and efficient underground operations. The capabilities of SC2.1 are directly applicable to multiple real-world scenarios where human access is dangerous, slow, or impossible, such as SAR missions in collapsed e.g. tunnels, exploration and inspection tasks in GNSS-denied environments, safety assessment after disasters.

Figure 5. Visualization of the position of the SPIDER and the video stream from the UGV visualized in the XR COMMAND tool (provided by LAAB).

Demo leader: Virtual Vehicle Research

Partners involved: AVL, HUAWEI Technologies Sweden AB, Pumacy, Universidad de Alcalá, Montanuniversität Leoben, Ostbayerische Technische Hochschuleamberg-Weiden, AIT Austrian Institute of Technology, Bundesministerium fuer Landesverteidigung und Sport, EDI - Institute of Electronics and Computer Science, Laabmayr

Demonstrator SC2.2 entirely operates in simulation representing a simulation-based robotic platform and the operation environment within SC2 focusing on cooperative multi-robot system. A high-fidelity simulation model of ZaB and SC2.1 were developed enabling two or more UGVs to collaboratively localize and map a subterranean environment. The virtual attribute of the demo offers scalable and flexible development opportunities for testing advanced multi-agent strategies and communication-oriented behaviours without the logistical constraints and safety risks of physical deployment.

The Demo comprises a complete simulation environment that models underground tunnel conditions, UGV operation, and communication effects. A detailed model of the ZaB tunnel facilities based on LiDAR measurements was developed within SC2.2, representing connected highway and railway tunnel tubes. Two UGV models are available in simulation, a Turtlebot4 platform and the SPIDER vehicle, including designated sensor characteristics. The multi-robot localisation and mapping modules allow at least two agents to build a shared representation of the tunnel environment. The effects of communication on multi-robot SLAM systems are covered in a conducted simulation study focusing on communication delay, de-synchronization and packet loss. Mitigating communication link failures between robots and/or a communication centre, an AI-based Quality of Service (QoS) prediction model is developed, providing forecasts of communication performance and blind spots at different locations.

SC2.2 introduces several innovations that advance the state of the art in subterranean SAR robotics:

- Cooperative multi-robot SLAM in GNSS-denied environments: SC2.2 demonstrates how multiple UGVs jointly localize and map the ZaB tunnels without GNSS.
- Communication-aware decision-making: A future integration of the QoS prediction into the navigation and coordination modules of the UGV will allow the agents to adjust their strategy to maintain reliable data exchange.
- Simulation framework for subsurface SAR scenarios: SC2.2 provides a flexible and scalable validation and testing environment for evaluating algorithms and models before deploying them onto real systems, reducing development risks and costs.

The SC2.2 simulation-based demonstrator offers broad potential for applicability reaching from SAR research and robotics development over to safety-critical planning, such as research on GNSS-denied localisation and sensor fusion; pre-mission planning and optimisation before first responders enter hazardous environments; training and validation of AI-driven multi-agent coordination algorithms; etc.

Figure 6. SPIDER operating in one highway tunnel tube executing a SLAM algorithm (Fast-LIO2).

Demo leader: Virtual Vehicle Research
 Partners involved: Universidad de Alcalá, Montanuniversitaet Leoben, Ostbayerische Technische Hochschuleamberg-Weiden, AIT Austrian Institute of Technology, Bundesministerium fuer Landesverteidigung und Sport

Figure 7. Example of reconstructed map using multi-robot SLAM with a fleet of 4 robots.

SC5: Quantum Sensor Multi-Modal, Multi-Physical Sensing at Highest Precision

Quantum sensing using NV-Centres in diamond

SC5.1

Quantum technologies are commonly grouped into three major domains: quantum computing, quantum communication, and quantum sensing. While quantum computing promises transformative capabilities for solving complex computational problems and quantum communication aims to provide fundamentally secure information transfer, quantum sensing is currently the most mature of the quantum technology domains and the closest to broad practical adoption. A-IQ Ready brings quantum sensing from laboratory prototypes to industrial and commercial applications. Specifically, we focus on Nitrogen Vacancy (NV) centre defects in diamond, which can be used to develop ultra-precise magnetometer sensors, and have the unique capability to operate at room temperatures. We join our interdisciplinary expertise to:

- improve “out-of-the-box” usability of the sensor,
- reduce its size and costs,
- and achieve the world’s fastest readout (while preserving advantageous performance).

Figure 8. A-IQ Ready's quantum sensor system and sensor miniaturised fibre-based sensor head design.

Measurements for underground/indoor localisation

In our recent indoor localisation tests, we explored the potential of quantum sensor magnetometers for precise spatial measurements. The study was conducted over two iterations to assess the reliability and accuracy of the technology in dynamic environments. For the second iteration, we took a step further by automating the process, leveraging a ground-truth OptiTrack positioning system alongside a robot to ensure consistent and repeatable measurements. This enhanced approach allowed us to refine our data collection methods and minimise human error. In the data, you can observe a magnetic field anomaly, likely caused by a structural element of the building, which highlights the sensitivity of the quantum sensor in detecting even the smallest variations in the environment. This anomaly is an interesting finding, demonstrating the complexities involved in indoor localisation and the power of quantum sensors in uncovering hidden details within physical spaces.

Figure 9. Setups for initial and automated magnetic field mapping tests. (a) Initial tests at the premises of VIF; (b) Sensor deployment on automated robot platform; (c) Indoors magnetic field mapping at EDI's automated testing rig; (d) EDI's ground-truth positioning system used for test automation.

Measurements for motor control

This motor control use case presents a fascinating challenge, as it involves a quantum sensor that requires an exceptionally high framerate for accurate measurements. To tackle this, we integrated the fibre-based sensor head of the quantum sensor directly inside a motor, a complex task that required precise engineering. During our tests, we gathered data that demonstrated the sensor's ability to track and determine the motor's phase. This breakthrough is significant, as it opens up new possibilities for using quantum sensors in real-time motor diagnostics and control systems.

Figure 10. Measurement setup for motor control tests using a quantum magnetometer. (a) Measurement setup; (b) Measurement data illustrating the motor's rotation phase; (c) Fibre-based sensor head concept.

Next steps

The advancements achieved in our quantum sensor development already provide a highly valuable input for the continued evolution of the technology, particularly within Chips-JU Horizon Europe initiatives such as ARCHIMEDES, Cynergy4MIE, and MOSAIC. Insights gained from these projects have directly informed the refinement of both system design and implementation strategies. Notably, the analogue electronics circuitry we developed is now undergoing miniaturisation, marking an important step toward more compact and scalable solutions. In parallel, we have introduced an optimised event-driven control hardware architecture, designed to enhance efficiency and responsiveness. Together, these developments represent a significant stride toward practical, deployable quantum sensing systems that can meet the demands of real-world applications.

Figure 11. Miniaturisation effort of quantum sensor's analogue electronics.

SC7: Cooperative Multi-Agent Systems (Decentralized AI for Emergent Industrial Solutions)

AGV system

SC7.1

The technical system of Demonstrator 7.1 has been successfully implemented in the laboratory environment of Proto_lab. In close collaboration between Safelog and THRO, the automated guided vehicles (AGVs) and the necessary peripheral components, such as charging stations and actuators for automated gate control, have been installed and tested. This step represents a significant advancement in the development of the AGV system.

As part of the implementation, a shift from **WIFI** to **5G** communication infrastructure was carried out. This measure aims to substantially improve the performance of data transmission between various hardware components and the control system. Tests have demonstrated that 5G technology offers stable connections and faster data rates, which are crucial for the efficiency of the overall system.

The cloud-based control system was established by our project partner ScaliRo. In this context, THRO programmed the travel paths, routes, and internal processes to compare them with the reference use case FT06. Continuous testing during the implementation phase allowed for further optimization of the overall system performance.

A standout result of this phase is the reduction of the throughput time using a standard controller to manage a FT06 pass. With a seamless operation, the throughput time was optimized to approximately **1 hour and 50 minutes**. This represents a significant improvement in efficiency.

Additionally, the use of the controller from WP 4, which includes a newly developed AI controller, was also successfully tested in the simulation environment of the **ScaliRo Cloud**. The performance of this new technology was slightly better in terms of throughput time compared to the previously used standard controllers from ScaliRo.

Overall, the current status of Demonstrator 7.1 shows that all technical components are working seamlessly together, and the set goals regarding system optimization have largely been achieved. The close collaboration of project partners has proven vital for the success of this implementation. The next steps will focus on integrating the insights gained into the further development of the AGV system and conducting additional tests to validate stability and performance under real-world conditions.

Figure 12. Setup of the training environment.

Figure 13. Technical implemented fleet of AGVs in the laboratory environment.

Overview:

We deliver a modular virtual training platform that trains, evaluates, and verifies reinforcement-learning (RL) navigation policies for autonomous mobile robots in challenging warehouse environments. The toolchain integrates a Unity-based digital twin, Nav2-inspired model-based controllers, specification-driven reward shaping, and ontology-based scenario generation into a reproducible pipeline for offline-to-online RL and automated validation.

Developments:

- Simulation & tooling (TUM): Procedural Unity environments with configurable physics, lighting, and appearance randomization; multi-modal sensors (RGB BEV/front, LiDAR, IMU, experimental quantum magnetometer model); deterministic annotations and a gRPC API for state/action exchange. Packaged as Docker images for on-premises use.
- Control & data pipeline (TUM): ROS2-decoupled Nav2-inspired controllers (A*/local planner/DWA) for baseline behavior and supervised trajectory logging to bootstrap offline RL (TD3-BC) and subsequent online fine-tuning (PPO/SAC/online-TD3).
- Specification & monitoring (AIT): Hierarchical potential-based reward shaping (HPRS) and hybrid runtime monitoring (approximate + exact) that translate formal temporal requirements into dense rewards and automated oracles for safety checks.
- Ontology & test generation (TUG): Browser app to author ontologies, convert constraints into parameter sets, combinatorial generation (pairwise/3-wise), OpenSCENARIO bundles for compact, reproducible test suites and curriculum progression.

Key innovations:

- Structured realism: semantically constrained domain randomization (color palette spacing, probability-weighted lighting, physically coherent parameter ranges) to produce realistic, diverse training distributions that improve transfer.
- Disturbance & delay awareness: explicit disturbance channels and delay hooks in simulation, plus disturbance-aware representations in policies for more robust, delay-resolved control.
- Spec-to-reward integration: automated pipeline from formal requirements to prioritized shaped rewards, reducing manual reward engineering and enabling verified training.
- Reproducible, semantic testing: ontology-driven scenario generation yields machine-checkable regression suites and critical-scenario libraries for safety validation.

Applications:

- Intralogistics: AGV/AMR navigation, routing, docking, congestion management, and multi-robot coordination.
- Research & education: reproducible RL benchmarks, lab courses, and student projects.
- Industrial pre-validation: scenario-based risk assessment and pre-deployment testing for system integrators and operators.

Figure 14. Partner contributions for SC7 demo. 2.

Figure 15. Integration flow of components developed by each partner as a sequence diagram.

Figure 16. Scalable simulations with canonical colour randomization for robust agent training.

Education & Dissemination

CPS&IoT'2025 Summer School

On the 11th of June, 2025, The A-IQ Ready project coordinator, Reiner John, took centre stage at the CPS&IoT'2025 Summer School and delivered a compelling lecture titled "Future Technologies for Europe: AI+, Immersive Systems & Quantum Sensing." The talk spotlighted Europe's push for digital sovereignty and strategic autonomy through innovation in AI, immersive technologies, and quantum sensing.

Drawing on collaborative work from A-IQ Ready, Archimedes and Cynergy4MIE, Reiner John introduced a comprehensive vision of Europe's technological future. He illustrated how technology stacks—from foundational layers to application domains—are powering transformative use cases in health, mobility, and infrastructure: "Europe's future in technology must be rooted in responsible, explainable, and effective systems. The next generation of researchers and developers are key to shaping this landscape".

The 6th Annual CPS&IoT Summer School offered a unique convergence of academia and industry in the fields of Cyber-Physical Systems (CPS) and the Internet of Things (IoT). The 2025 program spanned four days of intensive lectures, hands-on labs, demonstrations, and participation in CPSIoT 2025 and MECO 2025 conferences.

Figure 17. Reiner John (AVL) at CPS&IoT'2025 Summer School.

A-IQ Ready at Conferences

ICIPI 2025

On 16th–17th of October 2025, A-IQ Ready Project Coordinator Reiner John represented the project at the 26th International Conference on Industrial Technology Innovation (ICIPI 2025) in Taiwan.

During the conference, Reiner delivered a presentation titled "AI+ Systems and Quantum Sensing: Building Resilient Innovation – A European Vision for Taiwan's Strategic Partner." In his talk, he shared insights from ongoing Chips JU projects – A-IQ Ready, ARCHIMEDES, and Cynergy4MIE – highlighting how these initiatives are shaping the future of AI-driven and quantum-enabled technologies in Europe and beyond.

The conference provided an excellent platform to explore intercontinental collaboration and address key strategic questions:

- How can Taiwan and Europe combine their strengths in semiconductors, ICT, and robotics for mutual benefit?
- Which global tech trends will most influence future AI and robotics R&D priorities?
- Where can joint research and industrial applications emerge – from smart manufacturing and healthcare to robotics and sustainable mobility?
- What policy instruments and cooperation platforms best support long-term collaboration?
- How can we co-develop innovation ecosystems, talent exchange programs, and pilot projects to strengthen shared global leadership?

The event moved beyond discussion toward practical steps for collaboration, marking another milestone in A-IQ Ready's mission to connect European innovation with global technology partners.

Figure 18. Reiner John (AVL) at ICIPI 2025.

EF ECS 2025

On the 3rd-4th of December, 2025, the A-IQ Ready project was presented at EF ECS 2025 in Malta. On the first day of the conference, the coordinator, Reiner John, delivered a pitch presentation that showcased cutting-edge innovations and impactful A-IQ Ready results. This year, at our booth A-IQ Ready partner Alfonso Rodríguez from UPM presented a novel CGRA hardware accelerator.

EF ECS 2025, Europe's key event for electronic components, systems, and semiconductors, brought together around 700 policymakers, industry leaders, and researchers from across Europe, reaffirming its role as a key platform for shaping Europe's electronic components and systems agenda. Discussions throughout the event focused on translating strategic ambition into concrete outcomes through coordinated action across research, innovation, and industry.

The central themes of EF ECS 2025 – Europe's decision to pursue a distinct strategic path, the tangible progress being made under the EU Chips Act, and the growing importance of collaboration across the value chain.

Figure 19. A-IQ Ready representation at EF ECS 2025.

Strategic & Clustering Events

Quantum Sensing Workshop 2025

On the 10th of December, 2025, A-IQ Ready, Archimedes and Cynergy4MIE partners gathered in Erlangen for the 2nd Quantum sensor workshop. The workshop was jointly organised by Katrin Al Jezany and Reiner John (AVL List GmbH), together with Prof. Dr.-Ing. Roland Nagy from the Institute of Applied Quantum Technologies at FAU Erlangen-Nürnberg. A-IQ Ready, Archimedes and Cynergy4MIE projects representatives, along with partners from the MOSAIC project, presented progress across the entire chain of applications within the Chips JU programme. A-IQ Ready progress in Quantum Sensing was presented by Julio Posada from ARQUIMEA.

The main goal of the event is to discuss the past year's progress in the field of quantum sensing, potential applications, and challenges. The Workshop offered a clear message: quantum sensing is likely to become the first quantum technology to reach real-world markets. In contrast to quantum computing or quantum communication, quantum sensing technologies are significantly closer to being engineered into robust, certifiable and commercially viable systems.

A key takeaway emerged across all discussions: quantum sensing has evolved from a topic of fundamental physics into a semiconductor-driven and systems-oriented discipline. Bridging the gap between laboratory prototypes and real industrial products requires the convergence of five essential semiconductor building blocks:

- **Photonics** – integrated optics for excitation, readout and signal routing;
- **Wide-bandgap technologies** – particularly diamond and SiC as robust sensor and power platforms;
- **Digital CMOS** – enabling control, calibration and safe system integration;
- **High-precision analogue and mixed-signal front-ends** – essential for capturing ultra-weak quantum signals;
- **Hybrid, heterogeneous package integration** – combining photonics, wide-bandgap, digital and analogue components into industrial-grade modules;

With focused investment, quantum sensing could unlock more than €1 billion in impact in defence, medicine and automotive applications, strengthening Europe's position at the intersection of semiconductor and quantum technologies.

Figure 20. Quantum Sensing Workshop 2025 participants.

Beyond Horizons: Intelligent Mobility for Safe, Secure, and AI-Driven Future

The TechTalk 2026, hosted at TTTech in Vienna, brought together leading experts, researchers, and industry stakeholders for two days of forward-looking discussions on the future of automotive, edge systems, and emerging technologies.

Initiated by the A-IQ Ready coordinating team—Reiner John and Katrin Al Jezany from AVL List GmbH—the event created a dynamic platform for knowledge exchange, collaboration, and strategic alignment across key domains shaping next-generation intelligent systems.

Across two days of in-depth sessions, participants explored the future of mobility, safety, and AI-driven innovation. Discussions covered functional safety and validation concepts for critical systems, Cooperative, Connected and Automated Mobility (CCAM), and the broader mobility landscape. Attendees examined how physical AI and intelligent agents are transforming industries, alongside breakthroughs in high-speed networking, modular architectures, and the evolution toward responsible robotics powered by advanced processors and chiplet-based designs.

The programme also addressed forward-looking topics such as quantum technologies, distributed knowledge systems, and cybersecurity in a post-quantum world, all framed within the context of current and upcoming funding opportunities and constraints.

Active participation and insightful contributions from attendees further enriched the discussions, reinforcing the event's collaborative spirit.

TechTalk 2026 was jointly organized by leading industry and research organizations, including AVL List GmbH, Infineon Technologies AG, TTTech, NXP Semiconductors, BMW, CEA, Renault Group, Silicon Austria Labs, Harokopio University of Athens, Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg, Virtual Vehicle Research GmbH, and Fondazione Chips-IT, with support from ITML.

Figure 21. Reiner John (AVL) gives a presentation at TechTalk2026.

Figure 22. TechTalk2026 participants.

Search & Rescue Clustering Event

On 26 February 2026, the A-IQ Ready, ARCHIMEDES, and Cynergy4MIE projects jointly organised a Search & Rescue Clustering Event at Zentrum am Berg in Eisenerz, Austria. The event brought together stakeholders and researchers to explore synergies across projects, share insights, and foster collaboration in robotic Search & Rescue (SAR) technologies.

The programme featured interactive discussions on artificial intelligence, robotics, and emergency response. Attendees experienced project showcases and live demonstrations within the Zentrum am Berg tunnels, where robotic agents performed survivor detection, localisation, and maintained reliable communication with the operations centre. Indoor demonstrations further highlighted simulation-based solutions for communication systems, Multi-Agent Simultaneous Localisation and Mapping (Multi-Agent SLAM), and robust perception technologies.

The event provided an excellent platform for collaboration among the participating projects while showcasing tangible progress achieved under real-world conditions. Live demonstrations emphasised the seamless integration of various robotic platforms—UGVs and UAVs operating in complex environments—supported by resilient communication pipelines and advanced data management and visualisation tools. Seeing these technologies operate in unison clearly illustrated the overarching vision: how the combined technical innovations of multiple partners can interoperate as a unified system to effectively support first responders during emergency missions.

By bringing together the EU-funded projects ARCHIMEDES, AIQ Ready, and Cynergy4MIE, the Search & Rescue Clustering Event 2026 offered a unique opportunity for knowledge exchange and demonstrated how complementary technologies can be integrated into operational emergency response solutions. The event underscored the importance of system-level integration, interoperability, and cross-project collaboration in strengthening Europe's technological capabilities for Search & Rescue missions and advancing coordinated innovation across the continent.

Figure 23. Search & Rescue Clustering Event.

A-IQ Ready Consortium

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Learn more about the project

